

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16414336

Stabilization Policy And A Developing Economy The Nigerian Perspective

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of stabilization policy on a developing economy, where money supply and total expenditure were applied as proxy for stabilization policy. It was also discovered all the variables were positive skewed. Indicating that they are statistically significant.

Keywords: Economies, challenges, sustainable, institutional, instruments, policies, adjustments.

INTRODUCTION

Stabilization policy is viewed as a strategy put forward by the government or her economic planners in its ability of maintaining a healthy economy which involves monitoring the business cycle by either adjusting fiscal and monetary policies. These are put in place with the aim of achieving macroeconomic objectives in the economy to prevent major fluctuations that may affect economic growth and other distortions. Furthermore, stabilization policy seeks to limit erratic savings in an economy and as such stabilization policy is used to describe government actions in response to economic crises or shocks [Akinyede, 2007]. These are carried out through emergency actions or reforms that will be put forward by the economic manager by developing policies that are aimed at bringing about macroeconomic balance to the economy. In the views of Hayes [2021], he asserted that macroeconomic stabilization policy aims at creating a healthy levels of economic growth coupled with minimal price change. Thus, such policies are designed to prevent spiral effects on the economy. This position is further upheld by [Ejeh, 2018]. But CBN (2010) where of the view that economic growth is considered as the end target of economic stabilization policy taking cognizance of interest and inflation rates. Thus, this policy is aimed at controlling key macroeconomic parameters because they play a critical role in managing various fluctuations in the economy. Furthermore, the importance of stabilization is considered based on its ability to achieve and improve various economic basics and prevent economic crises.

Therefore, to sustain stabilization policy, the monetary authority must be prepared to monitor the business cycle and also put in place structures that could adjust fiscal and monetary policies that are required to control changes in supply and demand. In the views of CBN (2019), stabilization policy helps in reducing savings in vital aspects of the economy in the areas of inflation or deflation with the aim of attaining healthy levels of economic growth. These indicates that stabilization policies are instruments used to indicate actions that are applied in areas of economic crises or areas of shock. While in Nigeria, the aim

of stabilization policy is to ensure a stable economy which will include managing macro economic fluctuations which will also recognize promotion of sustainable economic growth. But Hayes, (2021) opined that stabilization policy is considered to aim at maintaining a healthy level of economic growth which will also affect price changes. And as such, the policy is aimed at controlling the economy from going to the extreme of economic upheavals which will depend on the level of price adjustment due to fluctuations with the aim of stabilizing the economy to enhance economic direction in the right direction and maintain price stability by controlling inflation. While in a developing economy, it is concerned with achieving full employment and price stability, coupled with economic growth. But the overall position is to stabilize the economy on managing the business cycle, achieve full employment among others.

This policy also creates conducive environments for business to thrive where investors could make informed economic choices. Stabilization policy consists of two majors' policy frameworks which are fiscal and monetary policies. These policies can also be used to control other anticipated imbalances that may be experienced in the economy.

An economy is considered as developing where it has low human development index, less growth, poor per capital income, higher population growth, poor infrastructure coupled with rising unemployment rate. Thus the citizens of these countries are either dependent on the government to have a better life through her policies. And as such these economics experience a great deal of economic volatility as a result of structural weakness and general inadequate institutional capabilities. Such economies have weak institution and men who are considered to be supermen and are considered to be above the law. In these nations, stabilization policies could be applied to correct or reduce the impact of these challenges and further lay good foundation for sustainable economic development. These economies have various forms of economic challenges, they also lack robust institutional frameworks and in appropriate governance structure coupled with highly compromised legal system.

Therefore, stabilization policy is considered as a deliberate change in government policy instruments which will have a major impact on a nation's economy. Stabilization policies are basically supported on both fiscal and monetary policies. In the view of Ekeh (2018) he asserted that stabilization policy is considered as a strategy taken by the government with the aim of maintaining a healthy level of economic advancement.

Based on the above, Hayes (2021) also asserted that macroeconomic stabilization policy is aimed at maintaining a healthy level of economic growth and price control and as such stabilization policy requires a proper check on the business cycle with appropriate adjustment in fiscal and monetary policy. This is because monetary authorities also develops policies that are aimed at bringing a balance to the economy. Therefore, there is an acceptable position that this policy leads to keeping the economy at check through the control of inflation, uncertainty and also attract foreign investment. And as such, the importance of stabilization policies are based on its ability in addressing economic imbalances. Towards this backdrop, policy makers view policies that can lead to a balance between short, medium and long term growth objectives, with aim of removing supply bottleneck and other forms of economic structural rigidities. And as thus the extent to which such rigidities that are observed in an economy will either influence whatever output that is considered in determining financial balance. Therefore, policy makers should be able to identify what is viewed as structural rigidities and propose an appropriate strategy for dealing with them.

In designing economic policies for Nigeria as a developing country, the policy makers should be concerned on how to reduce export on primary products and also reducing its foreign transactions to net exports which is believed would act as a booster to the economy. The study applied fiscal and monetary policies as proxies for stabilization policy and GDP for the Nigeria economy.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Stabilization policy is considered as strategy developed by a government to balance an economy and correcting certain structural rigidities in an economy.

Stabilization policy is also concerned with measures taken by the monetary authorities to apply various measures taken with the aim of maintaining or restoring balance, prevent fluctuations or predict various economic distortions within the economy. This is done with the aim of maintaining stable and sustainable economic growth by minimizing various forms of negative impacts of economic distortions and to further prevent excessive inflation (CBN, 2010) while Oyefusi, (2018) asserted that the principle guiding stabilization policy is to limit short term deviations in the system through long term market equilibrium. This point was explained by the position taken by Akayede and Elumah. (2017) where they opined that stabilization policy is considered based on government action which is aimed at controlling national income. Thus, stabilization policy is concerned with the use of fiscal and monetary policy tools by governments and central banks to moderate all aspects of economic fluctuations in any given economy.

And as such these policies are concerned with managing the business cycle and checking recessions and other forms of inflation and pressure. This position is further upheld by Bakare (2012) where he asserted that stabilization policy is considered by the government to be very important because policy makers applied as a tool for a centrally planned economy.

But in a developed economy, the following instrument are applied which are listed as follows:

Interest rates, control of credits and loans and requirements for cash reserves or reservation. Therefore, when an economy experienced challenges of various economic outcomes, the monetary authorities develops stabilization policies which are aimed at restoring such economic rigidities. Key aspects of stabilization policy includes fiscal policy and monetary policy. These policy instruments arc applied by the government and policy makers to shape the economy and achieve desired policy goals. Furthermore, these instruments must have direct or indirect impact on the economy which are command and control policy instruments, economic instruments information based instruments and voluntary instrument.

These are carried out with the aim of keeping the economy at check and as such stabilization policy helps in stabilizing the economy through effective control of aggregate demand and supply in the economy. In the views of fielding (2008) he asserted that stabilization policy is considered as the modification of economic policies by governments to support economic growth and development. Thus, stabilization policy is seen as remedy applied by the government to manage price fluctuations that are considered harmful to the economy. In an attempt to stabilize the economy, the government pursues three different goals which has to do with (a) Stabilize price volatility (b) attain full employment and (c) Achieve economic growth. This is important because government remains crucial in every development process, it also plays an important role in the functioning of the economy. In the views of World Bank (2015) they asserted that most developing and developed economy uses public expenditure to improve on their distribution of income, direct allocation of resources and further influence the composition of natural income. While Gupta (2018) opined that developing countries use government spending to spur economic growth and also expand employment opportunities.

This is because monetary authority of any country applies its monetary policy framework to manage the supply and the cost of money with the aim of either influencing the quantity and availability of money in circulation thus it is considered as a deliberate action. While fiscal policy is considered as the use of government generated revenue through a taxes and expenditure to influence aggregate spending in economy. Monetary policy is considered as working through price to achieve its macroeconomic goal indicating the effectiveness of monetary policy. In this study therefore, total expenditure was applied as proxy for fiscal policy and money supply was applied as proxy for monetary policy.

Government spending refers to money spent by the public sector on the provision of goods and services (Ahuja and Pandit 2020). And as such, it is considered as an important vehicle for the government to bring about development. All these are considered as an important variable in the operations and

functioning of an economy. In the view of he asserted that in a developing like Nigeria, government spending aids economic growth and development (Babatunde, 2018). While money supply refers to the total volume of currency held by the public at a particular point in time which is also regulated by the central bank. In the views of Omodero (2019), precious and Palesa (2014) they opined that money supply is considered to be an important element because it is viewed to be an important element for the betterment of an economy. Therefore, money supply can affect the economy either positively or negatively due to its significant impact on macroeconomic variables.

Model Specification

This study adopted econometrics method of data analysis data for this study was obtained from CBN’s statistical bulletin. the study also covered a period of 35 years (1985-2020). In furtherance to the above, a model was developed as thus:

$$GDP = F(MS, TE)$$

which was also transformed into an algorithm as $\log(GDP) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log MsIF + \beta_2 \log TEif + \epsilon IF$

Where $\log(GDP)$ = The log of gross domestic product at constant basic prices.

Log MS = Money Supply

Long TE = Total Expenditure

ϵif = Error term

β_0 Constant term

β_1 Estimate parameters

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 shoes the descriptive statistics for the macroeconomic variables under investigation, while figure 1 shows the time series plot for the variables. From table 1, GDP averaged 41,475.05 billion over the sampled period , while average values of money supply and government expenditure are N9,088 billion and N3,658 billion respectively. Also, the skewness and kurtosis coefficients indicate that all variables have a positively skewed, fat-tailed distribution, while the JB statistics strongly rejects the null hypothesis of normal distribution for all variables.

From figure 1, as expected, the three macroeconomic variables trended upward over time and hence requires transformation to achieve stationarity.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for GDP, MS, and TE

Statistic	GDP	MS	TE
Mean	41475.05	9088.03	3657.58
Max	202365.00	48462.07	24431.21
Min	139.31	14.47	9.64
Std Dev.	55932.01	13281.91	5900.24
Skewness	1.34	1.42	2.14
Kurtosis	3.70	3.90	6.76
Jarque-Beta	13.37	15.60	56.88
Prob. (JB)	0.0012	0.0004	0.0000

Figure 1: Time Series Plot for log GDP, Log MS, and Log (TE)

Stationarity Test

Table 2 shows the ADF stationarity/unit root tests for GDP, MS, and TE. The lag selection is based on Schwarz information criterion. For all variables, the ADF test statistic is not significant for the level series, while it is significant for the first difference series. This clearly shows that the variables all are integrated at order 1.

Table 2: ADF unit root tests

Variable	Level	Difference	Remark
LGDP	-1.4549 (0.5460)	-3.5004 (0.0131)	I(1)
LMS	-1.0723 (0.7176)	-4.1857 (0.0021)	I(1)
LTE	-0.8743 (0.7861)	-7.8056 (0.0000)	I(1)

Empirical Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	P-value
Model Estimates		
Constant	0.4307	0.0001
LGDP(-1)	0.9418	0.0000
LGDP(-2)	-0.0195	0.9368
LGDP(-3)	-0.2994	0.0471
LMS	0.2330	0.0053
LTE	0.1147	0.0163
Diagnostic Statistics		
R-squared	0.9989	
Adjusted R-squared	0.9987	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.1610	
BG (LM) statistic	2.2253	0.3287
BPG Heteroskedasticity	9.1400	0.1036

From table 3, the LGDP(-1) and LGDP (-2) are statistically significant, while LGDP(-1) is not statistically significant. The coefficients of 0.9418, -0.0195 AND -0.2994 show that a percentage increase in the current GDP would lead to about 0.94% increase in GDP in the next period, and about 0.092% and

0.30% decrease in GDP in the second and third periods. Hence, the net own effect of a 1% increase in GDP after three consecutive periods is 0.62%, which is substantial and economically significant. This clearly shows that the Nigerian GDP is highly predictable on the basis of its previous performance. Also, the speed of adjustment coefficient (CointEq(-1)) is negative and highly significant, indicating that the fitted ARDL model is stable and has long run implication. The coefficient of -0.3770 shows that GDP would adjust back to its equilibrium level after suffering a shock, and about 38% if this adjustment would occur in the next period.

Both LMS and LTE have positive values and are statistically significant. This shows that money supply and government expenditure are instrumental for the observed positive GDP trend. However, the coefficients of 0.2330 and 0.1147 show that money supply is more positively related to GDP to increase by about 0.23%, while a percentage increase in government expenditure would lead to about 0.11% increase in GDP. This provides strong empirical evidence that the Nigerian economy responds more to monetary policy than fiscal policy.

From Panel B, the Durbin Watson statistic does not deviate significantly from 2 and it is much greater than the R-squared, suggesting that our empirical results are not spurious. The F-ratio is highly significant and shows that GDP is strongly affected by the joint influence of money supply and government expenditure. Both the BG (LM) statistic and the BPG statistic are not statistically significant, implying that the fitted ARDL model is not plagued by serial correlation and/or heteroskedasticity. In other words, there is no misspecification error in our model.

CONCLUSION

The study shows that the variables trended upward over time and as such there was the need for stationary text. In the stationary text, all the variables were integrated at order 1. Therefore, the Nigerian economy responds to instruments of both monetary and fiscal policies. Thus, making the model acceptable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study considered the effect of stabilization policy on a developing economy, this has made it imperative for the monetary authorities and economic planners to do a lot in this direction and as such they should be proactive in monitoring the business cycle and also consider policies that will aid in adjusting both monetary and fiscal policies based on the current disposition of economic realities. These to a larger extent will aid and maintain a healthy economy that will lead to growth.

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